

A HOLISTIC FRAMEWORK FOR CRIME PREVENTATION, RESPONSE, AND ANALYSIS WITH EMPHASIS ON WOMEN SAFETY USING TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIETAL PARTICIPATION

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Abstract:

Our major contribution is in developing a holistic system encompassing the 3 crucial aspects, i.e crime analysis and mapping, crime hindrance, and emergency response by investment social participation for girls safety management. This work applies the Geographic system (GIS) for the identification of hotspots and patterns of crime. The projected system uses knowledge generated from the mobile application and/or wearable appliance prototyped as a locality of this work beside the criminal history records for crime response, analysis, and hindrance

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender-based disparities are unit one in every of the main problems with the present century. Despite the fact that constitutional rights have vouched for gender equality, it's a reality that gender-based inequality exists in many sections of societies across the planet. The 21st-century girls ought to a particular extent succeeded in contributive to

society and dealing shoulder to shoulder with men in many fields. However, violence against girls is being progressively according in recent times across the planet. In step with Antonio Guterres, the ninth Secretary-General of the world organization, violence and abuse against girls are unit among the world's most horrific human rights violations,

touching one in each three girls within the world. Gender equality is that the requirement for a higher world. ninth Secretary-General of the world organization, violence and abuse against girls area unit among the world's most horrific human rights violations

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Building safer cities for women requires holistic measures for crime prevention, analysis, and response. This will be effective only with the understanding of various socio-economic factors that lead to violence against women so that effective measures for social reforms can be designed. Also, technological interventions will not be effective in providing timely help if only law enforcement agencies or personal contacts are involved in rescue and response.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Rechargeable safety torch with shock result may be a awfully handy contrivance for all females. The light-emitting diode hidden electrical flashlights will have a awfully sturdy impact on humans. This personal protecting device ought to be thought of a vital a part of the women's bag. Safelet could be a wearable feminine security device with 2 buttons on the facet which will be accustomed send messages and get in touch with oldsters. It additionally starts voice recording in synchronize with the user's portable. within the event of a dangerous scenario, affected members UN agency receive the alert will

now dial the emergency range from at intervals the app.

DISADVANTAGES

- The non-parametric nature of the response under examination data does not presume a specific functional form.
- Other variables, such as the number of origin-destination pairs and the forecast horizon, may also affect predictability.
- The forecasts were based on a few crucial characteristics.
- K-nearest Neighbor, Support Vector Machine, and Multiple Linear Regression are the algorithms used.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Women's safety has been one of the top priorities for law enforcement agencies for several decades. Police departments around the world are facing demands to adopt newer solutions to handle the concern of women's safety. Various measures have been undertaken even in the past by police and public, through initiatives such as the starting of the dedicated police wings for woman safety, numerous mobile applications, severe punishments for offenders, etc. Other than dialing the police control room, the mechanisms available for women to seek help can be classified into two categories-smartphone assisted 'app' ba. Women's safety has

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Sets, read All GIS ladies Safety Crime kind, transfer Trained knowledge Sets,

ADVANTAGES

1. A guided learning method to discover the benefits of having a schedule and an actual arrival time
2. Algorithms have a low computational cost.
3. Based on a set of factors, we design a system that forecasts airline departure delays. Algorithms Used: Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting.

MODULES

- Service supplier
- Remote user
- View and Authorize Users
- Model Execution

DESCRIPTION OF MODULES:

Service supplier :

The Service Provider has got to login by mistreatment valid user name and positive identification. once login prosperous he will do some operations like - Login, Train and consider GIS ladies Safety knowledge Set Details, notice GIS ladies Safety magnitude relation on knowledge

Remote user:

during this module, there square measure n numbers of users square measure gift. User ought to register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details are going to be hold on to the info. once registration prosperous, he has got to login by mistreatment approved user name and positive identification.

View and Authorize Users:

during this module, the admin will read the list of users United Nations agency all registered. In this, the admin will read the user's details like, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Model Execution:

With the help of machine learning models like gradient boosting regression, logistic regression, decision tree regression, bayesian ridge, random forest regression, and Bayesian ridge, we can predict the outcome. The MSE is suitable for our regression issues since it is differentiable, which adds to the algorithmic stability. Additionally, it severely penalises larger errors relative to smaller errors. An indicator of risk, MAE provides the predicted value of the absolute error loss. This method measures the Explained Variance Score, or

the degree to which our machine learning model explains the scattering of the dataset. R2 Rating This statistic assesses the likelihood that the model will be able to predict unknown samples through the proportion of explained variance. It indicates the quality of fit. The best possible result is 1.0 and score can also be negative.

V. RESULTS

VI. CONCLUSION

Building safer cities for women requires holistic measures for crime prevention, analysis, and response. This will be effective only with the understanding of various socio-economic factors that lead to violence against women so that effective measures for social reforms can be designed. Also, technological interventions will not be effective in providing timely help if only law enforcement agencies or personal contacts are involved in rescue and response. The work presented in this paper describes the holistic framework for crime prevention, response, and analysis with emphasis on women safety using technology and societal participation..

VII.FUTURE WORK

Women safety has to be our priority. It's important for everyone - from the government to corporates and individuals – to join hands and to make India a safer place for women to work and live.

Crime Prevention comprises strategies and measures that seek to reduce the risk of crimes occurring, and their potential harmful effects on individuals and society, including fear of crime, by intervening to influence their multiple causes.

This project will help in the above aspect which reduces the crimes and gives prior information before entering the particular region

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